

1 **Chromatin remodeling enzymes are mobilized by Xist repeat deletion.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We recently demonstrated control of DNA damage signaling by Xist, as deletion of an Xist element
7 resulted in H2AX silencing. We present evidence here for interaction of Xist with the nuclear chromatin
8 remodeling machinery. BANF1 and a SWI/SNF component were silenced concurrent with H2AX silencing
9 resulting from Xist element deletion. Xist mobilization of chromatin remodeling enzymes is likely
10 multi-layered and complex.

11 Citations

12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
1. Bolderson, E., Burgess, J.T., Li, J., Gandhi, N.S., Boucher, D., Croft, L.V., Beard, S., Plowman, J.J., Suraweera, A., Adams, M.N. and Naqi, A., 2019. Barrier-to-autointegration factor 1 (Banf1) regulates poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 1 (PARP1) activity following oxidative DNA damage. Nature communications, 10(1), p.5501.